

Conference Abstract

Pensoft's ARPHA Publishing Platform top innovations in OA publishing as demonstrated by Subterranean Biology

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Abstract

There are three key challenges that need to be addressed by journal publishers nowadays:

1. increasing machine-readability and semantic enrichment of the published content to allow text and data mining, aggregation and re-use;
2. adopting open science principles to expand from publication of mainly research articles to all research objects through the research cycle, and
3. facilitating all of this to authors, reviewers and editors through novel and user-friendly technological solutions.

ARPHA stands for: Authoring, Reviewing, Publishing, Hosting and Archiving, all in one place. ARPHA is the first publishing platform to support the full life cycle of a manuscript within a single online collaborative environment.

The platform consists of two interconnected but independently functioning journal publishing workflows:

- ARPHA-XML: Entirely XML- and Web-based, collaborative authoring, peer review and publication workflow;
- ARPHA-DOC: Document-based submission (PDF, or text files), peer review and publication workflow.

A full list of services provided by ARPHA is available at: <http://arphahub.com/about/services>

Furthermore, Pensoft has been heavily investing in the technological advancement of its journals. The most significant technologies implemented by Pensoft as demonstrated also by the journal [Subterranean Biology](#) in the recent years are:

- Automatic registrations of reviews at Publons - Publons helps reviewers and editors get recognition for every review they make for the journal;
- Dimensions - powerful tracker of citations, which provides ranking of given research in a given field;
- Scopus CiteScore Metrics - interactive tool providing information on journal's performance;
- Export of published figures & supplementary materials to Biodiversity Literature Repository at ZENODO - increases visibility and traceability of article and sub-article elements;
- Hypothes.is - tool allowing annotations on selected texts from the published article.

Presenting author

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